

CFD Analysis for Nozzle Performance Evaluation for Various Materials

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Abstract—In industrial applications, steam nozzles are crucial for issues relating to flow. In order to optimise the flow over the nozzle, the current topic studies a convergent-divergent nozzle for various flow characteristics, forms, and materials. The performance of the convergent-divergent nozzle should be examined using a number of performance parameters, including the pressure ratio, flow parameters, nozzle size, and inlet pressure. Pressure distribution, velocity distribution, wall shear, flow characteristics, drag force, and drag coefficient are among the output parameters being examined in the current investigation. CFD analysis was used to address the problem while accounting for the energy equation and the k-model. The study's findings include: Steel is the most suitable material for the current application based on the coefficient of drag; material doesn't affect the pressure inside the nozzle for given input parameters; velocity is also roughly staying the same; material doesn't affect the temperature inside the nozzle for given input parameters; Mach Number for Aluminium & Steel materials is better than Titanium; and material doesn't affect the Wall Shear inside the nozzle for given input parameters. Overall, it can be said that steel and aluminium materials are more appropriate for the present use.

Keywords: Steam nozzles, convergent-divergent nozzle, Nozzle dimensions, Inlet pressure, Flow Parameters, Pressure Ratio, pressure distribution, Velocity Distribution, Wall Shear, Flow characteristics, Drag Force & Coefficient of Drag, k-ε model & energy Equation

I. Introduction

Generally speaking, fluid flow is the movement of a fluid under various unbalanced forces. It is primarily a component of fluid mechanics, and fluid flow generally addresses the fluid's dynamics. The fluid keeps moving until it is subjected to various imbalanced forces. There are four types of fluid flow: viscous, non-viscous, steady, and unstable. The fluid's velocity is constant when there is steady fluid flow at any point along the course. However, when fluid flow is unstable, the fluid's velocity fluctuates between any two sites. Viscosity is a measurement of a fluid's thickness, and there are many different types of viscous fluids, like shampoo and oil. When a flow is uniform, its velocity should always be the same between two points at any given moment, both in terms of magnitude and direction. When a flow is non-uniform, however, its velocity varies from point to point at any given time.

A nozzle is a device used to regulate the direction or properties of a fluid flow as it enters or leaves an enclosed chamber or conduit, particularly to enhance velocity. A nozzle can be used to control or alter the flow of a fluid (liquid or gas), and it is often a pipe or tube with a variable cross-sectional area. Nozzles are widely used to regulate the mass, shape, speed, direction, flow rate, and/or pressure of the stream that comes out of them. The fluid's pressure energy is sacrificed in a nozzle as its velocity rises.

A nozzle is merely a specifically designed tube that allows hot gases to pass through, making it a rather basic instrument. But the math that explains how the nozzle works requires some careful consideration. Nozzles can vary in size and shape based on the aircraft's mission, as seen above.

ANSYS is an analytical software program that is categorised as a FEA software package. It is utilised for the pre-processor

section, which develops the various geometry parts, applies the material, and creates a distinct coordinate system.

Fig. 1 Common type of Convergent-Divergent Nozzle

The study of fluid flows by numerical solution techniques is known as computational fluid dynamics, or CFD. Complex problems involving fluid-fluid, fluid-solid, or fluid-gas interaction can be analysed by CFD. Aerodynamics and hydrodynamics are two engineering domains where CFD analyses are commonly employed to determine quantities like lift and drag or field properties like pressures and velocities.

Physical laws in the form of partial differential equations are engaged in fluid dynamics. These principles are converted into algebraic equations by sophisticated CFD solvers, which can then effectively solve these equations numerically.

II. Problem Definition

The procedures to be taken for the CFD simulation and analysis of the current situation are shown in Fig. 2. Here are the steps for your reference-

- A. Concept Generation: As stated in the dissertation's first chapter, the process begins with the creation of a pertinent concept pertaining to the subject.
- B. Literature Review: In order to determine the goals of the present research project, the second phase in the procedure

is to review the literature that is currently available. The second chapter of the dissertation contains a thorough evaluation of the literature.

C. CAD Data Preparation: The next stage after determining the goals is to create a CAD 3D model of the nozzle with the required measurements. Various models are created for the current research project. Different nozzle angles have been established in order to optimise the flow pattern over the nozzle, and nozzles have been constructed in accordance with these settings. Nozzles have been produced in accordance with the selection of various cross-sections. Solidworks-2020, which is widely regarded as the greatest solid modelling software, has been used to complete model development.

D. Data Exchange: Solidworks 3D models are now imported into the ANSYS CFD module for analysis and conduction, and all solid models are converted to iges or step format for this reason. ANSYS is now using these format files for additional analysis.

E. Meshing: After the nozzle's 3D model is loaded into ANSYS, it is meshed in accordance with the ANSYS CFD module's shape and size. The majority of the time, while meshing any item in ANSYS, general settings are selected; nevertheless, there are a number of options available in ANSYS that can be altered, in addition to the size and shape of the pieces created by meshing.

Fig. 2 Flowchart of the Methodology to be Followed for the Current Research Study

F. Boundary Conditions: The next step in the ANSYS CFD module is to set up a number of boundary conditions, such as nozzle dimensions, inlet velocity, inlet pressure, nozzle shapes (circular, square, and rectangular), nozzle angles, area ratios, flow parameters, and pressure ratio, among others.

G. Problem Solving: The ANSYS CFD solver is designed to solve the problem after the boundary conditions have been established. To ensure that the solution converges and that the right answers are obtained, 300 iterations have been selected to solve the problem.

H. Post Processing: Following the resolution of the issue, a number of outcomes, contours, streamlines, and solution patterns are obtained.

I. Data Analysis: In this final stage of the process, the data is examined for a variety of permutations and combinations in order to determine the most practical solution for the nozzle analysis.

Fig. 3 A Common Setup of Convergent-Divergent Nozzle

III. Process Parameters

The performance of the convergent-divergent nozzle will be examined using a number of performance metrics. Here are the parameters that were taken into account for the current analysis for your reference-

- Inlet Parameters
 - Nozzle dimensions
 - Inlet pressure
 - Flow Parameters
 - Pressure Ratio
- Outlet Parameters
 - pressure distribution
 - Velocity Distribution
 - Wall Shear
 - Flow characteristics
 - Drag

IV. CFD Analysis Of Nozzle

The procedure of doing a thorough CFD analysis of a convergent divergent nozzle in ANSYS for its performance is explained in this section. The stages of the analytical process are as follows:-

A. Nozzle modelling: A 3D model of the nozzle was created using the CATIA software program. The CATIA design module is used to develop the model part. The nozzle's dimensions were previously discussed in the previous section.

Fig. 4 3D Model of the Nozzle Created in CATIA

B. *Importing Geometry*: The analysis step starts with opening the Fluid Flow Fluent in ANSYS following the development of the geometry in CATIA. Creating new geometry or importing pre-made geometry into any modelling program is the initial step in the analysis phase. The nozzle's current analysis geometry is loaded into the ANSYS Design Modeller from CATIA.

Fig. 5 Geometry imported in Design Modeler of ANSYS

C. *Body Operations*- The imported part undergoes two body processes, which involve cleaning and simplifying the imported body to eliminate any excess edges from the nozzles outside surfaces. Following these steps, the object is routed to the ANSYS Fluent meshing section.

D. *Meshing of the Nozzle*- The nozzle's 3D model is meshed in this section using ANSYS's default settings. The mesh element size is set at

Fig. 6 Meshing performed in ANSYS Fluent

After Meshing the component, different sections are named and converted in named selection section.

Fig. 7 Named Selection Creation in ANSYS

E. Finally, the analysis is run in ANSYS Fluent and results are observed.

V. Results & Discussion

- Results for Steel
 - Velocity Distribution

Fig. 8 Velocity Distribution for Steel

- Pressure Distribution

Fig. 9 Pressure Distribution for Steel

- Temperature Distribution

Fig. 10 Temperature Distribution for Steel

▪ **Wall Shear Distribution**

Fig. 11 Wall Shear for Steel

▪ **Velocity along the Axis**

Fig. 15 Velocity Distribution Along the Axis for Steel

▪ **Mach Number for Arrangement**

Fig. 12 Mach Number for Steel

▪ **Drag Force Distribution**

Fig. 16 Drag Force Distribution for Steel

▪ **Residuals For Steel**

Fig. 13 Residuals for Steel

▪ **Coefficient of Drag Distribution**

Fig. 17 Coefficient of Drag Distribution for Steel

The data gathered through the CFD analysis of the nozzle is presented in a tabular form as follows-

Table 1 Result Table

S. No.	Properties	Materials		
		Aluminium	Titanium	Steel
01	Velocity (m/s)	666.3	666.3	665.8
02	Temperature (K)	294	294	294
03	Wall Shear (Pa)	6643	6643	6643
04	Coefficient of Drag (C_d)	32568	31786	31799
05	Mach Number	4.24	3.08	4.24
06	Drag Force	17837	18695	18782

▪ **Pressure along the Axis**

Fig. 14 Pressure Distribution Along the Axis for Steel

A. Pressure Distribution

Fig. 18 Pressure Distribution

Above Fig. 18 Represents the distribution of Pressure for all three materials including Aluminium, Titanium & Steel after applying the initial boundary conditions. Results of the pressure distribution across materials reveals that maximum pressure inside the nozzle remains same for all the three materials. This shows that after applying initial pressure in the problem, Flow of working fluid across the nozzle remains unaltered for all the materials. This concludes that pressure of the working fluid is independent of the material that is being used.

B. Velocity Distribution

Fig. 19 Velocity Distribution

Above Fig. 19 Represents the distribution of velocity for all three materials including Aluminium, Titanium & Steel after applying the initial boundary conditions. Results of the velocity distribution across materials reveals that maximum velocity inside the nozzle remains nearly same for all the three materials as velocity of aluminium & Titanium is equal & that for steel changes from 667.3 to 666.8 only. This shows that after applying initial pressure in the problem, Flow velocity of

working fluid across the nozzle remains nearly unaltered for all the materials. Only for steel material a decrement of 0.5 m/s is observed. This concludes that velocity of the working fluid is larger when aluminium or titanium materials are being used that is being used.

C. Temperature Distribution

Below Fig. 20 Represents the distribution of temperature for all three materials including Aluminium, Titanium & Steel after applying the initial boundary conditions. Results of the temperature distribution across materials reveals that maximum temperature inside the nozzle remains nearly same for all the three materials. This shows that after applying initial pressure in the problem, temperature of working fluid across the nozzle remains nearly unaltered for all the materials. This concludes that temperature of the working fluid remains same for all materials for this input set.

Fig. 21 Temperature Distribution

D. Mach Number Distribution

Fig.22 Mach Number Distribution

Above Fig. 22 Represents the distribution of Mach Number for all three materials including Aluminium, Titanium & Steel after applying the initial boundary conditions. Results of the Mach Number distribution across materials reveals that Mach number is equal for Aluminium & Steel but reduces for steel material. This concludes that for the current application, Aluminium & Steel materials can be selected.

E. Wall Shear Distribution

Fig. 23 Wall Shear Distribution

Above Fig. 23 Represents the distribution of wall shear for all three materials including Aluminium, Titanium & Steel after applying the initial boundary conditions. Results of the wall shear distribution across materials reveals that wall shear is equal for Aluminium, Titanium & Steel all three materials. This concludes that wall shear of the working fluid is independent of the material that is being used.

F. Coefficient of Drag Distribution

Fig. 24 Coefficient of Drag Distribution

Above Fig. 24 Represents the distribution of Coefficient of Drag for all three materials including Aluminium, Titanium & Steel after applying the initial boundary conditions. Results of the Coefficient of Drag distribution across materials reveals that Coefficient of Drag is maximum for Steel which lowers for Aluminium then remains lowest for Titanium. This concludes that Coefficient of Drag of the working fluid is dependent of the material that is being used & Steel proves to be the best material out of the lot.

G. Drag Force Distribution

Fig.25 Drag Force Distribution

Above Fig. 25 Represents the distribution of Drag Force for all three materials including Aluminium, Titanium & Steel after applying the initial boundary conditions. Results of the Drag Force distribution across materials reveals that Drag Force is maximum for Steel which lowers for Aluminium then remains lowest for Titanium. This concludes that Drag Force of the working fluid is dependent of the material that is being used & Steel proves to be the best material out of the lot.

VI. Conclusion

Process parameter wise conclusion for the given set of inputs is as follows-

- Pressure distribution across the materials reveals no change in pressure value for all the materials which remains same at 96.96 bar (9.696×10^6). This shows that material doesn't affect the pressure inside the nozzle for given input parameters.
- Velocity distribution across the materials reveals minute variation in velocity when steel material is used which otherwise remains equal for other two materials. For steel material velocity is 665.8 m/s whereas aluminium & Titanium present a velocity of 666.3 m/s. One can presume that velocity is also approximately remaining same.
- Temperature distribution across the materials reveals no change in temperature value for all the materials which remains same at 294 K. This shows that material doesn't affect the temperature inside the nozzle for given input parameters.

- Mach Number distribution across the materials reveals that for Aluminium & Steel remains same as 4.24 and for Titanium it remains to be equal to be 3.08. Hence For the current application Aluminium & Steel materials can be used.
- Wall Shear Distribution across the materials reveals no change in Wall Shear value for all the materials which remains same at 6643 Pa. This shows that material doesn't affect the Wall Shear inside the nozzle for given input parameters.
- Coefficient of Drag distribution for all the materials reveals Coefficient of Drag is highest for Steel material at 18782 which reduces for Aluminium at 17837&18695 for Titanium. It reveals that Steel is best suited material for the current application.

Overall, it can be concluded that Aluminium as well as Steel materials are better suitable for the current application.

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